

STUDY OF UZBEK AND KARAKALPAK LITERARY RELATIONSHIPS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15779444>

Abstract. This article examines the history of the study of Uzbek and Karakalpak literary relations. The theoretical foundations of literary relations between the literatures of blood-related peoples are analyzed.

Keywords: Uzbek literature, Karakalpak literature, folklore, lyrics, socialization, artistry, literary influence.

Turkic peoples, including the Uzbek and Karakalpak peoples, have created rich literary traditions over the millennia of historical and cultural development. The literature of these peoples has determined not only the spiritual world of their people, but also the general trends of the entire Turkic world and world culture. As Aziz Nesin noted, the greatness of each people is determined by its cultural heritage. Therefore, the historical experience and literary heritage of the Turkic peoples are of great importance even today.

Due to the harsh influence of the ideological policy of the Soviet era, in-depth study of the national cultural heritage and its promotion were limited for many years. However, thanks to independence, an opportunity arose to understand national identity, return to history, and restore mutual cultural cooperation. The fact that the principle of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan “Literary friendship is eternal friendship” is supported at the level of state policy today is a vivid example of this.

The Uzbek and Karakalpak peoples have long lived in the same territory, in the same cultural space, and have developed in close connection with each other's language, religion, customs, and literary traditions. Literature has served as the most vivid expression of these historical and social ties. Such figures of Uzbek literature as Alisher Navoi and Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur had a strong influence on Karakalpak literature. In particular, the reflection of Navoi's work in the work of Karakalpak poets such as Berdaq, Ajiniyoz, and Oteshquli, and the fact that they wrote commentaries on Navoi's ghazals, testify to the depth of the literary dialogue.

Also, the fact that Berdaq, one of the famous names in Karakalpak literature, was inspired by the Uzbek literary environment and put forward pan-Turkic ideas in his work confirms the naturalness and harmony of literary relations between the two peoples.

The issue of scientific study of Uzbek and Karakalpak literary relations has become a separate direction in literary studies since the second half of the last

century. Kamol Mambetov's 1968 candidate's dissertation, Bakhtiyor Kurbanboyev's monograph "Berdaq and Uzbek Literature", and G. Kurambayeva's doctoral research are important scientific achievements in this regard. Through them, the processes of mutual literary influence, translation activities and aesthetic assimilation are deeply analyzed.

Today, the need to develop Uzbek-Qarakalpak literary relations in the new historical context, within the framework of the ideology of independence, on the basis of an integrative approach is increasing. The main directions in this regard are:

- Implementation of joint literary projects (anthologies, translations, conferences);
- Conducting research on the classical and modern literature of the two peoples;
- Organization of mutual literary awards, festivals;
- Development of cultural programs that strengthen creative exchange and friendship between young writers.

The historical and cultural proximity of the Uzbek and Karakalpak peoples, the experience of literary cooperation and relations based on mutual respect - will undoubtedly expand further in the future and reach new levels. After all, literature is a bridge between nations, an important pillar of cultural unity and a symbol of eternal friendship.

Literary ties between the Uzbek and Karakalpak peoples have undoubtedly been formed and strengthened over many centuries. Their mutual cultural and literary cooperation is not only historical ties, but also serves to further enrich each other's literary and cultural heritage today. Through creative exchanges, translation activities and literary research, relations between the two peoples are reaching a new level. This process serves to strengthen the cultural unity between the Uzbek and Karakalpak peoples and preserve their common historical and cultural past. Also, literature is a bridge between nations and should become an important means of cultural ties leading to eternal friendship and cooperation.

It is difficult to imagine literary ties without the activities of individual creators. There are many creators who have had a significant impact on the strengthening of Uzbek-Qarakalpak literary ties and their development with their new works. Several works by famous poets S. Akbariy, B. Boykobulov, A. Abdurazzoq, G. Matyokubova, drawn from the life of the Karakalpaks, can serve as an example of our idea.

When it comes to nationality in fiction, most literary critics see it in traditions, national dress, activities, efforts, speech, and believe that it finds its embodiment in these cases. True, these cases are factors that determine nationality. However, it cannot be said that these means and factors in themselves fully express nationality. Because these are the outward manifestations of nationality. As is known, appearance is a form. And form never determines the essence of the matter. It is a tool that serves to define. Nationality is embodied, first of all, in the psyche. All other characteristics that determine nationality depend on it, stem from it. And the psyche is a divine force, spiritual nourishment that determines the nature and identity of a person. A person with a strong psyche does not deviate from the right path, does not renounce his faith. The characteristics characteristic of a nation, which are noted and emphasized in many sources, namely, the predominance of the spirit of living as a community; the strength of high respect for parents, neighborhoods; the community in general; love for the native language; respect for the elderly and the young; respect for women; patience and hard work; honesty, kindness, etc. All these characteristics are the product of the national psyche. Because these qualities do not come from the body of a person, but from his feelings. The hero of today's literature has this characteristic. The traditions of world literature and literary and cultural ties have a great influence on the diverse creative and stylistic research in the poetry of all peoples of the world. As a result, the weight of genres in the poetry of fraternal peoples has increased, the artistic structure, style of expression, content, composition of images have become richer, and attention is being paid to revealing the psyche of the lyrical hero. Identifying the poetic laws, features of stylization and artistic synthesis involved in such poetic changes is of great importance in proving the signs of artistic improvement based on mutual literary influence in the lyrics of fraternal peoples. In world literary studies, special attention is paid to the study of the thematic direction, artistic-compositional, linguopoetic features of the works being created, directly linking them with the worldview of the creator, and stylistic skill, and in this, special attention is paid to the synthesis of Western and Eastern folklore, classical and modern literary traditions. The new pathos is accompanied by the choice of artistic form, theme, motif, and image, and as a result, formal and stylistic research in the poetry of the nation is renewed in its own unique forms. Substantiating the typology and specificity of traditions in poetry, the similarities in formal and stylistic research and renewal, the place and role of literary influence in this, and the preservation of the national

mentality as a literary process through systematic analysis serves the theoretical and practical development of our literary studies. Like other nations, Uzbek and Karakalpak poetry was formed due to the socio-political upheavals of the early 20th century, the ruthless trampling of national culture by tyrants, the trampling of national values, honor, and the breaking of bonds of kindness between people. As a result, such artistic searches and attempts took on the form of a certain poetic process. As is known, the brutally tyrannical regime of the 20th century sought to keep national poets firmly in the grip of the same patterns. They looked at the world only through this pattern. The fear of repression restrained the minds of creators. Freedom of thought and speech was stifled. As a result, literature became artistically impoverished to a certain extent. The same mood, the same form and theme prevented poets from creating new metaphors. Worse, as a result, the poets of the nation also enjoyed the dominant principles of world literature for a long time.

It can be concluded that the ethnic, linguistic and cultural ties between the Uzbek and Karakalpak peoples are significant not only for their historical roots, but also for their influence on the development of global culture. These peoples, living in close and interconnected territories, presented each other with their cultural heritage. The exchange of literary works and examples of oral creativity preserved in the memory of the people, reflects the unity and mutual respect of these peoples.

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